

PQ4R Strategy towards Reading Comprehension Development

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ABSTRACT: This study attempted to find out the effectiveness of PQ4R Strategy in the development of reading comprehension among Grade 7 students. It also sought to determine the results of conducting pre-test and post-test in reading comprehension in terms of identifying fact and opinion, making inferences, getting the main idea, and self-questioning. Thus, it also sought to determine if there is a significant difference in the reading comprehension of respondents before and after the implementation of PQ4R Strategy.

This study employed the experimental method of research which made use of pre-test and post-test as the main gathering tools. The respondents of the study were selected 83 Grade 7 students at Malvar School of Arts and Trade for the school year 2022-2023.

From the findings, it revealed that the student-respondents got an overall mean of 3.80 with a standard deviation of 1.60 in identifying fact and opinion, overall mean of 4.37 with a standard deviation of 2.21 in making inference, overall mean of 3.11 with a standard deviation of 1.47 in getting the main idea, and overall mean of 2.58 with a standard deviation of 1.65 in self-questioning.

Furthermore, it revealed that the post-test scores of the respondents in reading comprehension are higher than their pre-test scores. The null hypothesis stating that “There is no significant difference in the reading comprehension of the respondents before and after the implementation of PQ4R strategy.” is rejected. There is a significant difference in the reading comprehension of the respondents before and after the implementation of PQ4R strategy.

KEYWORDS: PQ4R strategy, comprehension, inference, self-questioning

INTRODUCTION

After more than two years of education crisis due to the suspension of in-person classes, students in the Philippines were given the chance to transition, from distance learning to full implementation of face-to-face classes. One of the crises is about the difficulty of students to comprehend what they are reading. It is evident among those students who experienced studying at home without a stable internet connection. It may be hard for them because they just receive the modules and answer them by relying on what was written on the directions. It was one of the reasons why they fail a test because they don't know how to follow directions. Even though they had spent time preparing for the exam, they still ended up performing poorly. In this case, there is a chance that the problem may have been because they do not know how to study as no one is guiding them in doing so. Define abbreviations and acronyms the first time they are used in the text, even after they have already been defined in the abstract.

It is a good thing that as per DepEd Order No. 034, s. 2022, starting November 2, 2022, all public and private schools shall have transitioned to 5 days of in-person classes. No school shall be allowed to implement purely distance learning or blended learning except for those implementing Alternative Delivery Modes as provided in DO 21, s. 2019 (Policy Guidelines on the K to 12 Basic Education Program) and DO 01, s. 2022 (Revised Policy Guidelines on Homeschooling Program). This created a big opportunity for the students to go back to a normal classroom set up where they can meet their teachers in person and feel the presence of their guidance in studying.

Malvar School of Arts and Trade is one of the tech-voc schools which uses K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum as a guide in the teaching-learning process. English is taught four times a week with a duration of forty-five minutes per class period.

Students do a lot of reading most of the time, but it is not enough that they read. Oftentimes, they are also asked to answer some comprehension questions based on what they have read. They should also justify why their answers to these questions are correct. Other than that, there are also times when they will be obliged to make reactions based on what they have read. In doing so, they need to have a better understanding on how they can cite evidence and make reactions based on their reading materials.

As per Regional memorandum No.719 s.2022, in reference to DM-CI-2022-378, the Bureau of Learning Delivery (BLD) shall conduct a Pilot Testing of the Philippine Informal Reading Inventory (Phil-IRI) for Junior High School. This activity aims to administer the JHS Phil-IRI selections to select schools in CALABARZON and utilize the relevant results on the finalization of said materials. The Division of Batangas Province was scheduled last November 21 to 25, 2022.

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Based on the pre-observation during the first and second quarters of the school year 2022-2023, the researcher found out that most of the students have limited vocabulary to comprehend a variety of materials. Sometimes, they don't know the meaning of a word found in a text that's why they cannot get the author's idea. They were too lazy to check the dictionary because they were busy talking to their classmates. It made them feel that reading is a boring activity because they were not motivated. Most students have difficulty in understanding the structure of the text lest its aim. Sometimes they do not know how to read and answer the questions coming from the teacher. Aside from reading comprehension, another learning disability of students in basic reading is called dyslexia which need an effective strategy to understand what they read and to remember the details of what they have read. Based on these problems, there should be a strategy to be used by the teacher to help students enhance their reading comprehension. A strategy that can help students without disabilities improve their reading comprehension, and retention which is much needed.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study analyzed the use of PQ4R method that was introduced by E. L. Thomas and H. A. Robinson in 1972 to help students develop their reading comprehension skills.

PQ4R is an acronym for preview, question, read, reflect, recite, and review. It is sometimes called the "SQ4R method" which stands for survey, question, read, reflect, recite, and review. It is a process used for learning new information. It is based on the work of an educational psychologist named Francis P. Robinson who believed that students need to take a more active approach to learning. His experience has proven that this idea is true because by using this method, it can improve understanding of the material and can help to remember it better.

METHODOLOGY

The research design used in this study is quantitative research with the experimental method since the researcher conducted an experiment in a class and configured the data numerically. According to Creswell (2009), quantitative research is a method to test certain theories by examining the relationship between variables. These variables are measured usually with research instruments with the result that is composed of numbers that can be analyzed based on statistical procedures. To be precise, the design of the experimental method is called "One Group Pretest-Posttest Design" (Setiyadi, cited in Nadya, 2017). This method is about looking into the effectiveness of treatments by comparing samples' achievement from pre-test and post-test given.

This study was conducted to one group pre-test and post-test design to determine the effects of PQ4R strategy towards reading comprehension development among Grade 7 students.

RESPONDENTS OF THE STUDY

The researcher used the selected Grade seven students in Malvar School of Arts and Trade as the respondents of the study.

Distribution of Respondents in Malvar School of Arts and Trade

Table A

Grade 7 Sections	Frequency	Sample Size
7-Section A	47	47
7-Section B	47	0
7-Section C	46	0
7-Section D	45	0
7-Section E	46	0
7-Section F	45	0
7-Section G	48	36
7-Section H	45	0
7- Section I	47	0
7- Section J	47	0
7- Section K	46	0
7- Section L	46	0
TOTAL	554	83

As shown in Table A, the researcher got 83 respondents from Malvar School of Arts and Trade. With the total population of 554 grade seven students, the researcher utilized cluster sampling. The researcher got the sample members of 83 students in sections A and G.

Research Instrument

To elicit information needed in this study, the researcher used the following research instruments: a Researcher-made Pre-test and Post-test on reading comprehension skills aligned with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC) and a Lesson Exemplar for the Third Quarter.

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The items in the checklist were based on the readings done by the researcher. Questions were also based on the reviewed related literature and studies. It consists of three parts: Part I which contains the pre-test scores of the respondents in terms of: Identifying Fact and Opinion, Making Inference, Getting the Main Idea and Self-Questioning, Part II which contains the post-test scores of the respondents in terms of: Identifying Fact and Opinion, Making Inference, Getting the Main Idea and Self-Questioning, and Part III which contains the significant difference of PQ4R and the reading comprehension of the respondents.

Research Procedure

In the construction of the checklist, the researcher used pre-test and post-test instruments answered by the respondents. She looked for some questions about reading comprehensions that are aligned with the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELC). She also used a lesson exemplar as a guide to execute the study.

On the first day, the researcher administered the forty-item pre-test to the selected Grade 7 students and determined the result. The following day, she applied the PQ4R strategy in teaching reading to the class. This was done by following the six steps of PQ4R method. The first step is Preview. Before the students read, they looked at the pictures and captions. Then, they skimmed and scanned the text to get an idea by reading the first and last paragraph. The second step is Question. Students were advised to think of the information they got through skimming and scanning. After that, they were given time to ask questions about it. They were asked to think about what they already knew about the ideas they saw during their preview. They were asked to write down the questions in their notebook. The third step and the highlight of the method is Read. Students read the material extensively and they were asked to write down important points about what they have read. They jot down vocabulary words that were unfamiliar to them and they checked a dictionary to find the meaning. This enabled them to understand the text clearly. The researcher also asked them to construct sentences on their own using the vocabulary word learned. The next step is Reflect. This step gave the students time to reflect on what they have read. They were asked to think about the information they have learned. They have had some realizations of the information that surprised them. They were asked to write down the things they remembered about what they have read. Recite is the next step after reflecting. Students were asked to discuss the answers to the questions they have generated during the second step. They were asked to summarize the material by answering those questions using their own words. They explained it aloud to someone else and recited the notes aloud to themselves. The final step is Review. Students were asked to review all the answers to their questions. For some questions that were not answered, they were asked to read the material again. On the third day, the researcher followed the same steps in reading a new material. This was also done on the fourth and fifth day. The following week, she introduced a new lesson that tested another reading comprehension skill. The same steps were followed in reading a new material. This continued until the fifth day of the week, utilizing more reading materials for testing other reading comprehension skills. She administered the post-test to the same students who answered the pre-test after four weeks of applying the PQ4R strategy while following the lesson exemplar. Then, she looked for the result and analyzed the data gathered from the pre-test and post-test scores of the respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The discussion of the findings was patterned in the manner that coincides with the organization of the problems posted in this study.

1. On the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score of the Respondents in Reading Comprehension

1.1 In terms of Identifying Fact and Opinion

Table 1. Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores of the Respondents in Reading Comprehension in Terms of Identifying Fact and Opinion

Scores	PRE-TEST SCORES		POST-TEST SCORES		Verbal Interpretation
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	
9-10	--	--	4	4.82	Excellent
7-8	--	--	18	21.69	Very Good
5-6	22	26.51	27	32.53	Good
3-4	47	56.63	23	27.71	Poor
0-2	14	16.87	11	13.25	Very Poor
TOTAL	83	100.00	83	100.00	

Table 1 presents the pre-test score of the respondents in reading comprehension in terms of Identifying Fact and Opinion. It reveals that out of 83 student-respondents, 47 or 56.63% of them scored the highest which indicates that most of them have poor reading comprehension in terms of identifying fact and opinion during the pre-test. This implies that these number of students had limited knowledge on facts about the passage that they were about to read. After the application of PQ4R strategy, 27 or 32.53% of them scored the highest which indicates that most of them have good reading comprehension in terms of identifying fact and opinion during the post-test. This implies that these number of students had increased their knowledge on facts about the passage that they read after applying the PQ4R strategy. It is also evident from the table that there are 22 or 26.51% of students who increased in their scores and were able to meet the very good and excellent level of reading comprehension in terms of identifying fact and opinion during the post-test. This time they were able to determine which statements are facts because there was a proof that these could be

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found in the passage that they have read. They also determined which statements express an opinion because these cannot be found in the passage that they have read, instead these were expressed through a feeling or value judgement.

1.2 In terms of Making Inference

Table 2. Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores of the Respondents in Reading Comprehension in Terms of Making Inference

Scores	PRE-TEST SCORES		POST-TEST SCORES		Verbal Interpretation
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	
9-10	--	--	12	14.46	Excellent
7-8	--	--	23	27.71	Very Good
5-6	22	26.51	28	33.73	Good
3-4	47	56.63	13	15.66	Poor
0-2	14	16.87	7	8.43	Very Poor
TOTAL	83	100.00	83	100.00	

Table 2 presents the pre-test score of the respondents in reading comprehension in terms of Making Inference. It reveals that out of 83 student-respondents, 47 or 56.63% of them scored the highest which indicates that most of them have poor reading comprehension in terms of making inference during the pre-test. This implies that these number of students have limited knowledge in making a guess about what they don't know based on the information available. They don't know how to figure things out by applying their own knowledge and experience to the given situation. After the application of PQ4R strategy, 28 or 33.73% of them scored the highest which indicates that most of them have good reading comprehension in terms of making inference during the post-test. This implies that these number of students had increased their knowledge and textual information after applying the PQ4R strategy in reading. It is also evident from the table that there are 35 or 42.17% of students who increased in their scores and were able to meet the very good and excellent level of reading comprehension in terms of making inference during the post-test. This time they were able to draw conclusions, make critical judgements and form interpretations of the text.

1.3 In terms of Getting the Main Idea

Table 3. Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores of the Respondents in Reading Comprehension in Terms of Getting the Main Idea

Scores	PRE-TEST SCORES		POST-TEST SCORES		Verbal Interpretation
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	
9-10	--	--	5	6.02	Excellent
7-8	2	2.41	18	21.69	Very Good
5-6	13	15.66	29	34.94	Good
3-4	36	43.37	20	24.10	Poor
0-2	32	38.55	11	13.25	Very Poor
TOTAL	83	100.00	83	100.00	

Table 3 presents the pre-test score of the respondents in reading comprehension in terms of getting the main idea. It reveals that out of 83 student-respondents, 36 or 43.37% of them scored the highest which indicates that most of them have poor reading comprehension in terms of getting the main idea during the pre-test. This implies that these number of students had trouble in recalling important information from the text they have read. They cannot determine the primary point or concept that the author wants to communicate to the readers about a certain topic. After the application of PQ4R strategy, 29 or 34.94% of them scored the highest which indicates that most of them have good reading comprehension in terms of getting the main idea during the post-test. This implies that these number of students had enhanced their ability in finding the topic sentence when it was directly stated in the passage that they read. On the other hand, if the author did not directly state the main idea, they were able to capture it by looking closely at the content of the passage. It is also evident from the table that there are 23 or 27.71 % of students who increased in their scores and were able to meet the very good and excellent level of reading comprehension in terms of getting the main idea during the post-test. This time they were able to deduce what the author wants to communicate.

1.4 In terms of Self-Questioning

Table 4. Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores of the Respondents in Reading Comprehension in Terms of Self-Questioning

Scores	PRE-TEST SCORES		POST-TEST SCORES		Verbal Interpretation
	Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent	
9-10	--	--	13	15.66	Excellent
7-8	--	--	15	18.07	Very Good
5-6	12	14.46	29	34.94	Good
3-4	33	39.76	21	25.30	Poor
0-2	38	45.78	5	6.02	Very Poor
TOTAL	83	100.00	83	100.00	

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Table 4 presents the pre-test score of the respondents in reading comprehension in terms of getting the main idea. It reveals that out of 83 student-respondents, 38 or 45.78% of them scored the highest which indicates that most of them have very poor reading comprehension in terms of self-questioning during the pre-test. This implies that these number of students experienced difficulty in formulating questions about the paragraph that they have read. After the application of PQ4R strategy, 29 or 34.94% of them scored the highest which indicates that most of them have good reading comprehension in terms of self-questioning during the post-test. This implies that these number of students had increased their ability to learn independently. It enabled them to monitor their reading comprehension by asking themselves helpful questions after reading to check the understanding of the content. It is also evident from the table that there are 28 or 33.73 % of students who increased in their scores and were able to meet the very good and excellent level of reading comprehension in terms of self-questioning during the post-test. This time they were able to transform themselves from passive readers to active readers.

2. On the Significant Difference in the Reading Comprehension of the Respondents before and after the implementation of PQ4R Strategy

Table 5. Significant Difference on Reading Comprehension of the Respondents Before and After the Implementation of PQ4R Strategy

Reading Comprehension	Pre-test		Post-test		t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Verbal Interpretation
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD				
Identifying Fact and Opinion	3.80	1.60	5.02	2.19	-5.339	82	.000	Significant
Making Inference	4.37	2.21	5.98	2.32	-7.764	82	.000	Significant
Getting the Main Idea	3.11	1.47	5.18	2.23	-9.170	82	.000	Significant
Self-Questioning	2.58	1.65	5.70	2.39	-11.865	82	.000	Significant

Legend: Sig. (2-tailed) ≤ .05, (significant); Sig. (2-tailed) > .05, (not significant)

Table 5 presents the significant difference on reading comprehension of the respondents before and after the implementation of PQ4R Strategy.

After being taught, the students' reading comprehension using PQ4R Method was better than before using PQ4R Method. It was proved that the mean of post-test in the four reading comprehension skills: Identifying Fact and Opinion (5.02); Making Inference (5.98); Getting the Main Idea (5.18); and Self-Questioning (5.70) are higher than that of the mean of pre-test four reading comprehension skills: Identifying Fact and Opinion (3.80); Making Inference (4.37); Getting the Main Idea (3.11); and Self-Questioning (2.58). This indicates that the four reading comprehension skills of the students improved after applying the PQ4R method.

The increase in the mean score of Identifying Fact and Opinion implies that students had increased their knowledge on facts about the passage that they read. They were able to determine which statements are facts because there was a proof that these could be found in the passage that they have read. They also determined which statements express an opinion because these cannot be found in the passage that they have read, instead these were expressed through a feeling or value judgement.

In addition to, the increase in the mean score of Making Inference implies that students increased their knowledge and textual information after applying the PQ4R strategy in reading. They were able to draw conclusions, make critical judgements and form interpretations of the text.

Moreover, the increase in the mean score of Getting the Main Idea implies that students enhanced their ability in finding the topic sentence when it was directly stated in the passage that they read. On the other hand, if the author did not directly state the main idea, they were able to capture it by looking closely at the content of the passage. This time they were able to deduce what the author wants to communicate.

Lastly, the increase in the mean score of Self-Questioning implies that students increased their ability to learn independently. It enabled them to monitor their reading comprehension by asking themselves helpful questions after reading to check the understanding of the content. They were able to transform themselves from passive readers to active readers.

The results in the table above show that the four reading comprehension skills obtained a p-value of .000 which is lower than .05. This indicates that there is a significant difference in the reading comprehension of the student-respondents before and after the implementation of PQ4R Strategy. It implies that the reading comprehension of the students are measured by means of answering the pre-test and post-test allotted for each comprehension skill. It means that there is an impact of PQ4R Method on the students' reading comprehension.

In addition to, it proves that PQ4R strategy successfully increased the students' reading comprehension skills; the result of the post-test (the students' mean score) are higher compared to their scores in the pre-test. Students experienced difficulty when answering the pre-test because they still didn't have prior knowledge of the lesson and they were not familiar with some terms included in the

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pre-test. They just read the selection and answered the comprehension questions without analyzing them. After applying the PQ4R method, students followed the sequence.

It is not yet clearly understood that using PQ4R strategy in teaching reading is an effective tool. However, it helps students to improve their reading comprehension skill. This finding is same as with Syarifah (2016), Octaviani (2013), the application of PQ4R strategy to improve reading comprehension was effective, where the post-test score is higher than the pre-test score.

Finally, it was found from the experimental study at SMP Negeri 1 Karang Baru, Aceh Tamiang, that the use of PQ4R strategy in learning process is very useful to improve students' reading comprehension skill. Referring to the findings of this study, the score was significantly improved after the researcher had given the treatments. It could be seen from the score. The score of pre-test and post-test could be evidence of students' improvement. The PQ4R strategy really helps students in each aspect of reading.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In light of the significant findings, the following conclusion was drawn. The null hypothesis stating that "There is no significant difference in the reading comprehension of the respondents before and after the implementation of PQ4R strategy." is rejected. There is a significant difference in the reading comprehension of the respondents before and after the implementation of PQ4R strategy.

The following recommendations were based on the findings of this study:

1. For the Language Teachers, it is recommended that they utilize the PQ4R Strategy because the results revealed its effectiveness in teaching reading to the class.
2. For the Learning and Development Coordinators, it is recommended that they include "Utilizing PQ4R Strategy" in conducting training courses for teachers because it can help enhance their abilities, especially in teaching reading.
3. For Future Researchers, it is recommended that they conduct more studies about PQ4R Strategy and its importance in all stages of education, specifically in other areas or topics in language since the study is limited to reading comprehension.

APPENDIX

Appendixes, if needed, appear before the references.

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